

SOCIO ECONOMIC PORTFOLIO AND MARKETING OF PRAGATI MILK IN CUTTACK DISTRICT OF ODISHA

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Abstract

The present study was undertaken to know the Marketing cost and margins, Price spread, Marketing efficiency of Pragati milk. The study has been undertaken in the Nischintakoili block of Cuttack district. A total of 60 sample respondents are analysed. Among these 28 are small farmers, 23 are medium farmers and 29 are large farmers. For Pragati milk, in channel-I, the overall average net price received by the producer is Rs.45, and the consumer purchase price is Rs.54. In channel-II, the overall average net price received by the retailer is Rs. 51, and the consumer purchase price is Rs.54. Market efficiency revealed that for Pragati milk Market efficiency of channel-II is high with 7.85, and for channel -I was 5.92 per cent. Farmers should focus on the marketing channels where there are fewer intermediaries and can attain maximum profits. There is a need for an up gradation of the dairying technologies like for milking, usage of milking machines is more sophisticated than following the traditional methods.

Keywords: - Marketing efficiency, Price Spread, Socio economic, purchase price

Introduction

The Indian dairy & dairy products industry comprises milk and large variety of milk products like flavoured milk, ghee, butter, curd, butter milk, cheese, paneer, ice cream, etc. Milk consumption in India is regular part of the dietary programme in the country as it comes with healthy nutrients such as calcium, proteins, vitamins, phosphorus, etc irrespective of the region and hence demand is likely to rise continuously with sustainable growth potential providing health benefits such as maintaining normal blood pressure, strengthening bones and providing energy, repairing muscle tissues, etc. among many others. It contributes over 20% to the agriculture GDP of the country. India has also retained the leadership position in milk production by producing 188 million metric tonnes in FY19; accounting for about 22% of global milk production. Hence, dairy industry has played a crucial role in the agro-based Indian economy. Animal husbandry and livestock production is one of the major sources of income of Indian farmers and it has an important role in the Indian agricultural economy. The large ruminants namely cattle and buffalo are integral part of livestock sector followed by other small ruminant species. More than 70% Indian rural people rear

livestock and a majority of them are smallholders with less than 5 dairy animals (Birthal and Jha, 2005; Ghuman and Singh, 2009). The dairy farmer of the Nischintakoili maintains milch animals as a complimentary business to agriculture. The livestock farming provides self-employment, beneficiary income and a nutritious health to the society in rural as well as urban areas.

Research Methodology

Descriptive research design was adopted for the study as it describes the characteristics or phenomena that are being studied. The present study was conducted in Cuttack district. Out of 14 blocks in Cuttack district, Nischintakoili block is selected purposively based on maximum area covered under dairy farmers. From the selected block, five villages were selected purposively based on the maximum number of dairy farmers.

Objectives of the Study:

- 1- To assess the socio-economic profile of the respondents.
- 2- To determine the price spread and marketing efficiency in study area.

Results and Discussion**Table no. 1. Socio-economic profile of the respondents**

Sl. No	Independent variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Age	Upto 35 years	16	26.66
		36-45 years	21	35
		46- 55 years	15	25
		above 55 years	8	13.34
2.	Caste	General	25	41.66
		OBC	16	26.66
		SC & ST	19	31.68
3	Educational qualification	Illiterate	12	20
		Primary school	26	43.33
		Higher Secondary	20	33.34
		Graduate above	2	3.33
4	Size of Family	Small	28	46.66
		Medium	23	38.34
		Large	9	15
5	Number of Milch Cattle	Below 3	24	40
		3-5	19	31.66
		6-10	14	23.34
		Above 10	3	5
6	Average milk supplied per respondent	Up to 10 liters	39	65.00
		11- 20 litres	17	28.34
		20-40 litre	4	6.66

From the above table 1, it is shown that 35 per cent of the respondents belonged to middle aged group. Majority of the respondents (46.11

%) belong to general caste and 43.33 per cent respondents had primary level of education. It is evident that majority of the

respondents (46.66 %) has been living in small family. It was found that 40 per cent of respondents have less than three milch cattle. It

was found that 65 per cent of respondents supply up to 10 litre of milk per day

Table 2: - marketing margin, price spread in the milk marketing channel-I

Channel 1: Producer – Wholesaler – Consumer

Sl. No	Particular's	Average Value (Rs/ltr.)
1	Cost incurred by the producer	
	Procurement Price from farmer	36.00
	Processing	1.5
	Loading and unloading	0.8
	Transportation	0.9
	Miscellaneous Cost	0.8
	Sub Total (Total Marketing Cost)	4.0
	Producer Margin (Pragati Milk)	5.0
	Producer Selling Price	45
2	Cost incurred by the wholesaler	
	Purchasing price from producer	45.00
	Packaging and material Cost	0.2
	Transportation cost	0.5
	Marketing cost	0.4
	Labour cost	0.3
	Loading & Unloading cost	0.5
	Miscellaneous cost	0.2
	Sub Total (Total Marketing Cost)	2.1
	Wholesaler margin	6.9
Selling Price to Consumer	54	
	Marketing efficiency	7.85%
	Market margin for producer	13
	Market margin for wholesaler	11.1
	Net price of producer	40.0
	Price spread	14.0

Above table it is seen that the marketing price of the milk supplied by the farmer is Rs 36 and the net price received by producer is Rs 40. Meanwhile the cost incurred by the wholesaler in purchasing of milk was Rs 45 with a market margin of Rs 11.1 and the milk was

sold to customer at a price of Rs 54. Eventually, the price spread was seen to be Rs 14 per litre, the marketing cost was Rs 2.1, and marketing efficiency was 7.85%

Table 3: - marketing margin, price spread in the milk marketing channel-II

Channel 2: Producer – Wholesaler – retailer – Consumer

Sl. No	Particulars	Average value (Rs/ltr)
1.	Producer sale price to wholesaler	45
	Marketing cost incurred by the producer	4
	Producer Margin	5
2.	Wholesaler Margin	3.9
	Marketing cost incurred by wholesaler	2.1
	Wholesaler Price to retailer	51
3.	Cost incurred by the Retailer	
	Loading and unloading charges	0.3
	Carriage up to shop	0.5
	Transportation cost	0.5
	Miscellaneous cost	0.4
	Subtotal (Total Marketing Cost)	1.7
	Retailer Margin	1
	Retailer price to consumer	54
	Net price of producer	40.0
	Market margin for producer	13
	Market margin for wholesaler	8.1
	Market margin for retailer	4.7
	Marketing efficiency	5.92 %
Price spread	14.0	

In the above table, it was seen the price procured by the wholesaler was 45 rupees and the cost incurred by the retailer 51 rupees. The market margin for retailer is 4.7 whereas the marketing efficiency stands out to be 5.92 per cent and the price spread is 14 per litre

Table 4: Comparison of total marketing cost, total marketing margin, price spread and marketing efficiency in two different channels (Pragati milk) (Rs/ltr)

Sl. No.	Particulars	Channel-I	Channel-II
1	Total marketing cost	6.1	7.8
2	Total marketing margin	24.1	25.8
3	Price spread	14	14
4	Marketing efficiency	5.92%	7.85%

Table 4. reveal that total marketing cost in channel-I is Rs.6.1/ litre, price spread Rs.14/litre, marketing efficiency 5.92 percentage and the total marketing margin is 24.1 respectively. The total marketing cost in channel-II is Rs.7.8/litre, total marketing margin Rs.25.8/litre; price spread Rs.14, and marketing efficiency 7.85 percentage. This shows that the channel -II has a upper hand because total marketing cost, total marketing margin and marketing efficiency is comparatively more as compared to channel-I which depicts total marketing cost, total marketing margin and marketing efficiency for channel-II is 7.8, 25.8, 7.85% and for channel-I it is 6.1,24.1 and 5.92% respectively. Whereas both the channels have same price spread value i.e., 14.

Conclusion

It is concluded that the socio-economic profile of the sample group that majority of respondents belongs to 36- 45 years and are educated up to primary, belongs to general caste. Existing marketing channels of milk for Channel I involves producer, wholesaler, consumer and channel II involves producer, wholesaler, retailer, consumer. It was observed that market efficiency in channel-I was 5.92 per cent and channel- 2 was 7.85 per cent and price spread was 14 rupees. It is suggested that large farmers should use upgraded technologies like milking machines rather than hand pulling.

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